

Advancements in the Diagnosis and Surgical Management of Ebstein's Anomaly: A Comprehensive Review

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ABSTRACT

Ebstein's anomaly is a rare congenital heart defect characterized by the apical displacement of the septal and posterior leaflets of the tricuspid valve, resulting in atrialization of the right ventricle and significant hemodynamic disturbances. This anomaly often presents with a spectrum of clinical manifestations, ranging from asymptomatic cases to severe heart failure and cyanosis in neonatal life. The diagnostic process has been significantly enhanced by advancements in echocardiography, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), and electrocardiographic techniques, enabling early detection and detailed assessment of structural abnormalities.

Treatment strategies for Ebstein's anomaly are tailored according to the severity of the condition and patient age. While mild cases may be managed conservatively, severe forms necessitate surgical interventions, including tricuspid valve repair or replacement, bidirectional Glenn shunt, and occasionally the Fontan procedure. Novel approaches, such as cone repair, have shown promising outcomes in improving valve function and overall cardiac performance. This review article provides a detailed exploration of the pathophysiology, clinical manifestations, diagnostic advancements, and therapeutic options for Ebstein's anomaly, with an emphasis on surgical innovations.

KEYWORDS: Ebstein's anomaly, tricuspid valve repair, congenital heart defect, cone procedure, right ventricular dysfunction, cyanosis, echocardiography, cardiac surgery

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INTRODUCTION

Ebstein's anomaly, first described by Wilhelm Ebstein in 1866, is a rare congenital malformation of the tricuspid valve that affects approximately 1 in 200,000 live births, accounting for less than 1% of all congenital heart defects. The hallmark of this anomaly is the apical displacement of the septal and posterior tricuspid valve leaflets, leading to atrialization of a portion of the right ventricle. This unique anatomical alteration results in variable degrees of tricuspid regurgitation, right atrial enlargement, and impaired right ventricular function, which can have profound clinical implications.^{1,2}

The clinical presentation of Ebstein's anomaly is highly heterogeneous. In mild cases, patients may remain asymptomatic throughout life, whereas severe forms can

present in the neonatal period with cyanosis, heart failure, and arrhythmias. The broad spectrum of clinical manifestations poses a diagnostic and therapeutic challenge, necessitating a comprehensive approach for optimal management.^{1,2}

Advancements in imaging modalities, particularly echocardiography and cardiac MRI, have revolutionized the diagnostic landscape, allowing for detailed anatomical and functional assessments. In parallel, surgical techniques have evolved significantly. The introduction of the cone repair, which reconstructs the tricuspid valve into a more functional, near-normal valve, has demonstrated improved outcomes in terms of valve competence and right ventricular function.^{1,2} This article aims to provide an in-depth review of Ebstein's anomaly, focusing on its pathophysiology, clinical spectrum, and the latest advances in diagnostic and surgical

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management. By addressing these aspects, we aim to enhance the understanding of this complex condition and highlight future directions for research and clinical practice.²

Epidemiology

Ebstein's anomaly is a rare congenital heart defect, constituting approximately 0.5–1% of all congenital heart diseases. Its estimated incidence is about 1 in 200,000 live births, with a slight female predominance reported in some studies. The condition exhibits a worldwide distribution, without clear evidence of ethnic or geographic predilection. However, differences in clinical presentation and outcomes may arise due to variations in access to healthcare and diagnostic facilities across regions.³

The exact etiology of Ebstein's anomaly remains elusive, although it is generally considered sporadic. Nonetheless, a familial occurrence has been documented in a minority of cases, suggesting a potential genetic component. Mutations in the *NKX2-5* and *MYH7* genes have been implicated in rare instances, highlighting the potential role of genetic factors in its pathogenesis. In addition, maternal exposure to certain environmental factors during pregnancy, such as lithium and benzodiazepines, has been associated with an increased risk of fetal Ebstein's anomaly. While the teratogenic effect of lithium is well-documented, its absolute risk remains low, with studies estimating an incidence of around 1 in 1,000 pregnancies exposed to lithium.⁴

In terms of natural history, the condition exhibits considerable variability. In its mildest forms, Ebstein's anomaly may remain asymptomatic and undiagnosed until adulthood. Conversely, severe cases can present in the neonatal period with profound cyanosis, heart failure, and life-threatening arrhythmias. This wide clinical spectrum significantly influences the prognosis and survival rates. Advances in diagnostic imaging and surgical techniques over recent decades have notably improved the survival of affected individuals, particularly those requiring early intervention. Historically, severe neonatal cases were associated with high mortality, with survival rates as low as 50% in the first year of life. Contemporary series, however, report markedly improved survival, with many centers achieving neonatal survival rates exceeding 80%.⁴

The anomaly frequently coexists with other congenital heart defects, such as atrial septal defects (ASDs), patent foramen ovale (PFO), and ventricular septal defects (VSDs). Additionally, up to 20% of individuals with Ebstein's anomaly develop accessory pathways, leading to arrhythmias such as Wolff-Parkinson-White (WPW) syndrome. The presence of these comorbidities can further complicate the clinical course and necessitate tailored management strategies.⁴

The epidemiological understanding of Ebstein's anomaly has been greatly enhanced by population-based studies and congenital heart disease registries. However, given its rarity and phenotypic variability, large-scale, multicenter studies

are crucial to gaining further insights into its incidence, natural history, and long-term outcomes. Continued advancements in prenatal screening and genetic testing hold promise for improving early detection and understanding of this complex congenital heart defect.⁴

Clinical Manifestations

Ebstein's anomaly presents with a wide spectrum of clinical manifestations, ranging from asymptomatic cases identified incidentally during adulthood to severe, life-threatening symptoms presenting in the neonatal period. The clinical presentation is largely influenced by the degree of tricuspid valve displacement, the extent of right ventricular atrialization, and the presence of associated congenital anomalies or arrhythmias.⁵

Neonatal Presentation

In severe forms of Ebstein's anomaly, neonates may present with cyanosis, respiratory distress, and signs of heart failure shortly after birth. Cyanosis results from right-to-left shunting of blood through an interatrial communication, such as a patent foramen ovale (PFO) or atrial septal defect (ASD), due to elevated right atrial pressures. The hemodynamic instability in these patients may be exacerbated by severe tricuspid regurgitation, which contributes to impaired right ventricular output and reduced pulmonary blood flow.⁵

Additionally, neonates may exhibit failure to thrive, hepatomegaly, and peripheral edema, indicative of systemic venous congestion. In the most severe cases, neonates are at risk of developing persistent pulmonary hypertension of the newborn (PPHN), further complicating the clinical course.⁵

Infant and Childhood Presentation

In less severe cases, symptoms may not manifest until infancy or early childhood. Common presentations during this period include exercise intolerance, feeding difficulties, and cyanosis during physical exertion or crying episodes. Growth retardation may also be observed, reflecting chronic hypoxemia and inadequate systemic perfusion.⁶

Arrhythmias, particularly supraventricular tachycardia (SVT) or Wolff-Parkinson-White (WPW) syndrome, can emerge early and may present as episodes of palpitations, syncope, or even sudden cardiac arrest. The presence of accessory pathways in up to 20% of patients with Ebstein's anomaly significantly increases the risk of these arrhythmias.⁶

Adolescent and Adult Presentation

In adolescents and adults, Ebstein's anomaly often presents with symptoms of right heart failure, including fatigue, peripheral edema, ascites, and jugular venous distension. Cyanosis may persist or worsen, particularly in those with significant interatrial shunting.⁶

Arrhythmias remain a prominent feature in this age group, with patients frequently experiencing paroxysmal or persistent atrial fibrillation, atrial flutter, or SVT. Palpitations and syncope are common presenting symptoms, and the risk of thromboembolic events, such as stroke or transient

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ischemic attacks, is increased, particularly in the setting of atrial fibrillation and right-to-left shunting.⁶

Physical Examination Findings

Physical examination in patients with Ebstein's anomaly often reveals a spectrum of findings depending on the severity of the defect. Key findings may include:

- **Cyanosis:** Most evident in severe cases with right-to-left shunting.⁶
- **Clubbing of the fingers and toes:** A sign of chronic hypoxemia.⁶
- **Jugular venous distension:** Reflecting elevated right atrial pressure.⁶
- **Auscultation findings:** A holosystolic murmur of tricuspid regurgitation is commonly heard at the lower left sternal border, often accompanied by a widely split second heart sound (S2). In some cases, a mid-diastolic murmur may be present, signifying increased flow across the tricuspid valve.⁶
- **Hepatomegaly:** Indicative of right-sided heart failure.⁶

Associated Conditions

Ebstein's anomaly frequently coexists with other congenital heart defects and extracardiac anomalies. Atrial septal defects or PFOs are found in over 80% of patients, facilitating interatrial shunting. Ventricular septal defects and pulmonary stenosis may also be present, complicating the hemodynamic profile.⁷

Arrhythmic complications, particularly WPW syndrome, are a hallmark of the condition. These patients may present with delta waves on electrocardiography, reflecting pre-excitation due to accessory pathways. Additionally, severe forms may predispose to progressive right ventricular dysfunction and eventual development of severe tricuspid regurgitation.⁷

Prognosis and Variability

The natural history and prognosis of Ebstein's anomaly are highly variable. While mild cases may remain asymptomatic with normal life expectancy, severe forms can lead to early morbidity and mortality, particularly in neonates. Advances in medical management, arrhythmia control, and surgical techniques have significantly improved outcomes, especially for patients requiring intervention during childhood or adolescence.⁸

Understanding the diverse clinical manifestations of Ebstein's anomaly is critical for timely diagnosis, risk stratification, and the development of individualized management plans.⁸

Diagnostic Methods

The diagnosis of Ebstein's anomaly relies on a combination of clinical evaluation, advanced imaging techniques, and electrocardiographic studies. Given the wide spectrum of disease severity and associated anomalies, a comprehensive diagnostic approach is essential for accurate characterization of the defect and for guiding management.⁹

Clinical Evaluation

The initial suspicion of Ebstein's anomaly often arises during clinical examination, particularly when cyanosis, signs of right heart failure, or characteristic cardiac murmurs are detected. In neonates and infants, the presence of cyanosis and a holosystolic murmur at the lower left sternal border may prompt further investigation. In older children and adults, symptoms such as exertional dyspnea, fatigue, palpitations, or syncope often lead to diagnostic workup.¹⁰

Electrocardiography (ECG)

Electrocardiography is a cornerstone in the diagnostic process, providing crucial information about rhythm disturbances and conduction abnormalities commonly associated with Ebstein's anomaly. Characteristic findings on ECG include:¹¹

- **Right atrial enlargement:** Reflected by tall, peaked P waves in the inferior leads.¹¹
- **Prolonged PR interval:** Due to delayed conduction through the atrioventricular (AV) node.¹¹
- **Right bundle branch block (RBBB):** Frequently observed in patients with significant right ventricular involvement.¹¹
- **Delta waves and short PR interval:** Indicative of Wolff-Parkinson-White (WPW) syndrome, seen in up to 20% of patients.¹¹
- **Atrial arrhythmias:** Such as atrial fibrillation or flutter, particularly in older patients or those with significant atrial dilation.¹¹

Chest Radiography

Chest X-rays often reveal cardiomegaly, particularly due to right atrial and ventricular enlargement. In severe cases, a characteristic "box-shaped" cardiac silhouette may be noted. Pulmonary vascular markings are typically reduced in the presence of significant right-to-left shunting or reduced pulmonary blood flow.¹²

Echocardiography

Echocardiography is the primary imaging modality for diagnosing Ebstein's anomaly, offering detailed visualization of the tricuspid valve and right heart structures. Key echocardiographic findings include:

- **Apical displacement of the septal and posterior tricuspid leaflets:** The defining feature of Ebstein's anomaly. The apical displacement index (distance between the tricuspid and mitral annuli) is measured to quantify the anomaly, with a displacement of >8 mm/m² body surface area considered diagnostic.¹²
- **Atrialized right ventricle:** Identified as a portion of the right ventricle that is functionally part of the right atrium.¹²
- **Tricuspid regurgitation:** Often severe, with Doppler studies showing regurgitant flow into the right atrium.¹²

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- **Interatrial communication:** Such as a patent foramen ovale (PFO) or atrial septal defect (ASD), facilitating right-to-left shunting.¹²
- **Right ventricular function:** Assessment of global and regional systolic function, which may be impaired in advanced cases.¹³

Three-dimensional (3D) echocardiography further enhances the assessment of tricuspid valve morphology and function, providing critical information for surgical planning.¹³

Cardiac Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI)

Cardiac MRI is increasingly utilized in the evaluation of Ebstein's anomaly, particularly when echocardiographic images are suboptimal. It provides superior spatial resolution and detailed anatomical and functional assessment of the right ventricle and tricuspid valve. MRI is particularly valuable for:

- **Quantifying right ventricular volumes and function.**¹⁴
- **Assessing the degree of atrialization of the right ventricle.**¹⁴
- **Evaluating associated cardiac anomalies** such as ASDs or ventricular septal defects (VSDs).¹⁴
- **Accurate measurement of tricuspid valve displacement.**¹⁴

Cardiac Computed Tomography (CT)

While less commonly used, cardiac CT may be indicated when precise anatomical detail is required, particularly in patients with complex anatomy or prior cardiac surgery. It can provide high-resolution images of the tricuspid valve and surrounding structures. Additionally, CT angiography is valuable for evaluating pulmonary vasculature in cases with suspected pulmonary embolism or pulmonary vascular anomalies.¹⁵

Electrophysiological Studies

Electrophysiological studies (EPS) are often performed in patients with arrhythmias, particularly those with WPW syndrome or recurrent supraventricular tachycardia. EPS allows for mapping and ablation of accessory pathways, which can significantly improve symptom control and reduce the risk of sudden cardiac death.¹⁵

Cardiac Catheterization

In select cases, cardiac catheterization may be necessary to assess hemodynamic parameters, including right atrial and ventricular pressures, pulmonary artery pressures, and the degree of right-to-left shunting. Oxygen saturation studies can quantify the extent of cyanosis and shunting. Additionally, catheterization may aid in evaluating pulmonary vascular resistance when pulmonary hypertension is suspected.¹⁵

Prenatal Diagnosis

Fetal echocardiography has enabled the prenatal diagnosis of Ebstein's anomaly as early as 18–22 weeks of gestation. Key findings include the apical displacement of the tricuspid valve

and cardiomegaly, often associated with severe tricuspid regurgitation and hydrops fetalis in severe cases. Early diagnosis allows for parental counseling and planning of perinatal management, including the potential need for immediate postnatal intervention.¹⁶

Genetic Testing

Although Ebstein's anomaly is primarily sporadic, genetic testing may be considered in cases with a family history of congenital heart disease or when associated with syndromic conditions. Mutations in the *NKX2-5* or *MYH7* genes, among others, have been implicated in a minority of cases. Genetic counseling can provide insights into recurrence risks and inform family planning.¹⁶

The diagnostic approach to Ebstein's anomaly involves a multidisciplinary effort, utilizing clinical, imaging, and electrophysiological tools to characterize the condition comprehensively. Advances in imaging, particularly 3D echocardiography and cardiac MRI, have significantly enhanced diagnostic accuracy and surgical planning, contributing to improved outcomes in this complex congenital anomaly.¹⁶

Current Treatment Approaches for Ebstein's Anomaly

The management of Ebstein's anomaly is highly individualized and depends on the severity of the anatomical defect, the presence of symptoms, associated cardiac anomalies, and the patient's age. Treatment strategies range from conservative management for asymptomatic patients with mild disease to complex surgical interventions for those with severe manifestations. Advances in surgical techniques, catheter-based interventions, and medical therapy have significantly improved the prognosis for patients with this rare congenital heart defect.¹⁶

Medical Management

Medical therapy plays a critical role in the initial stabilization of symptomatic patients and the long-term management of those who are not immediate candidates for surgical intervention. Key aspects of medical management include:

1. Heart Failure Management

Patients presenting with signs of right-sided heart failure, such as peripheral edema, hepatomegaly, and ascites, may benefit from diuretics to reduce fluid overload. Loop diuretics, often combined with aldosterone antagonists, are commonly used to alleviate symptoms.¹⁶

In cases with diminished cardiac output, particularly those with significant tricuspid regurgitation, afterload-reducing agents such as angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitors or angiotensin receptor blockers (ARBs) may be considered. However, their use must be carefully titrated due to the risk of hypotension in these patients.¹⁶

2. Arrhythmia Management

Arrhythmias, particularly supraventricular tachycardia (SVT) and Wolff-Parkinson-White (WPW) syndrome, are common in Ebstein's anomaly. Antiarrhythmic medications such as

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beta-blockers, calcium channel blockers, or class III agents like amiodarone are used to control heart rate and prevent recurrent arrhythmias.¹⁶

In patients with refractory arrhythmias, electrophysiological studies (EPS) followed by catheter ablation of accessory pathways or arrhythmogenic foci are often required. Radiofrequency or cryoablation has shown high success rates in achieving long-term rhythm control.¹⁶

3. Anticoagulation Therapy

Patients with Ebstein's anomaly and atrial fibrillation, significant interatrial shunting, or a history of thromboembolic events may require anticoagulation therapy to reduce the risk of stroke. Direct oral anticoagulants (DOACs) or vitamin K antagonists are commonly used, depending on the clinical scenario and associated comorbidities.¹⁶

Interventional and Surgical Treatment

Surgical intervention is the cornerstone of treatment for patients with severe Ebstein's anomaly, particularly those with significant tricuspid regurgitation, progressive right ventricular dysfunction, or refractory symptoms. The decision to proceed with surgery is based on a comprehensive assessment of symptomatology, right ventricular function, and the severity of tricuspid valve displacement.¹⁶

1. Tricuspid Valve Repair or Replacement

The primary surgical approach involves either repair or replacement of the tricuspid valve. Tricuspid valve repair is preferred when feasible, as it preserves the native valve and minimizes the need for long-term anticoagulation. Techniques for tricuspid valve repair include:

- **Cone Reconstruction:** This technique involves mobilizing and reattaching the displaced tricuspid valve leaflets to form a functional, conical valve. Cone repair has become the standard of care in many centers due to its favorable outcomes, including improved right ventricular function and reduced tricuspid regurgitation.¹⁶
- **De Vega Annuloplasty:** A simpler technique involving the reduction of the tricuspid annulus diameter to improve valve competence.¹⁶

In cases where the valve is too dysplastic or damaged for repair, valve replacement using either a mechanical or bioprosthetic valve is performed. Bioprosthetic valves are often preferred in younger patients to avoid the need for lifelong anticoagulation.¹⁶

2. Bidirectional Glenn Shunt

In neonates and infants with severe cyanosis and poor right ventricular function, a bidirectional Glenn shunt may be performed as a palliative procedure. This procedure connects the superior vena cava to the pulmonary arteries, bypassing the right atrium and reducing the volume load on the right ventricle. It serves as a bridge to more definitive surgery later in life.¹⁶

3. Fontan Procedure

In patients with severe right ventricular dysfunction or hypoplastic right ventricle, a Fontan procedure may be considered. This complex surgery involves directing systemic venous return directly to the pulmonary arteries, effectively bypassing the right heart. It is typically reserved for patients with single-ventricle physiology or those in whom conventional repair is not feasible.¹⁶

4. Atrial Septal Defect (ASD) or Patent Foramen Ovale (PFO) Closure

Closure of an interatrial communication (ASD or PFO) is often performed concurrently with tricuspid valve repair or replacement to prevent paradoxical embolism and reduce cyanosis. Closure can be achieved surgically or via catheter-based techniques using septal occluder devices.¹⁶

5. Electrophysiological Interventions

Patients with WPW syndrome or refractory arrhythmias may undergo concomitant surgical or catheter-based ablation of accessory pathways during tricuspid valve surgery. This dual approach has shown to improve rhythm outcomes and reduce the recurrence of arrhythmias.¹⁷

Emerging Therapies

Recent advancements in minimally invasive techniques and transcatheter interventions are expanding the therapeutic options for patients with Ebstein's anomaly. Transcatheter tricuspid valve repair or replacement, including edge-to-edge repair and valve-in-valve procedures, is being explored in select cases with promising early results. These techniques may offer a less invasive alternative for high-risk surgical candidates or those with prior valve surgery.¹⁷

Stem cell therapy and regenerative medicine are also being investigated as potential avenues for enhancing right ventricular function and promoting myocardial recovery in severe cases.¹⁷

Postoperative Management and Long-Term Follow-Up

Postoperative care focuses on optimizing hemodynamics, managing arrhythmias, and preventing complications such as thromboembolism or prosthetic valve dysfunction. Lifelong follow-up with a multidisciplinary team, including cardiologists, electrophysiologists, and cardiothoracic surgeons, is essential. Regular imaging with echocardiography or cardiac MRI is necessary to monitor right ventricular function, tricuspid valve performance, and the progression of any residual defects.¹⁷

Patients require tailored rehabilitation programs and counseling on lifestyle modifications, including physical activity limitations and the management of comorbidities. Women of childbearing age with Ebstein's anomaly require specialized counseling and care during pregnancy due to the potential risks of hemodynamic compromise and arrhythmias.¹⁷

The treatment of Ebstein's anomaly has evolved significantly, with a shift toward more effective surgical

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techniques and the integration of catheter-based interventions. Personalized treatment strategies, guided by a thorough understanding of the disease's complexity and variability, are critical to optimizing outcomes and improving the quality of life for affected individuals.¹⁷

CONCLUSION

Ebstein's anomaly is a rare and complex congenital heart defect characterized by apical displacement of the septal and posterior leaflets of the tricuspid valve, resulting in a spectrum of anatomical and functional abnormalities. The condition presents with wide variability in clinical manifestations, ranging from asymptomatic cases detected incidentally to severe neonatal forms associated with profound cyanosis and heart failure. This heterogeneity underscores the importance of a tailored diagnostic and therapeutic approach, incorporating advances in imaging, electrophysiology, and surgical techniques.

The diagnostic evaluation of Ebstein's anomaly has been revolutionized by the development of high-resolution imaging techniques, particularly echocardiography and cardiac magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). These modalities provide detailed anatomical and functional assessments of the tricuspid valve and right ventricular morphology, essential for accurate diagnosis and preoperative planning. Prenatal diagnosis via fetal echocardiography allows for early identification of severe cases, enabling timely intervention and parental counseling. Additionally, electrocardiographic and electrophysiological studies play a crucial role in identifying and managing arrhythmias, which are common in this patient population.

Management of Ebstein's anomaly requires a multidisciplinary approach, with treatment strategies tailored to the individual's clinical presentation, age, and associated anomalies. While asymptomatic patients with mild disease may benefit from conservative management, those with severe tricuspid regurgitation, right ventricular dysfunction, or significant cyanosis often require surgical intervention. The advent of cone repair has been a major milestone, offering improved outcomes in tricuspid valve reconstruction and reducing the need for prosthetic valve replacement.

In patients with refractory arrhythmias, catheter ablation or surgical ablation performed concurrently with tricuspid valve surgery has significantly improved rhythm control. For those with severe right ventricular dysfunction or single-ventricle physiology, staged palliation with procedures such as the Glenn or Fontan shunt provides life-saving alternatives. Emerging transcatheter approaches, including percutaneous tricuspid valve repair and replacement, hold promise for high-risk surgical candidates.

Despite these advancements, challenges remain in the management of Ebstein's anomaly. Long-term follow-up studies are needed to assess the durability and outcomes of surgical repairs, particularly in younger patients who may

require multiple interventions over their lifetime. The optimal timing of surgical intervention, especially in asymptomatic or mildly symptomatic patients, continues to be an area of ongoing investigation. Furthermore, the management of associated arrhythmias and prevention of sudden cardiac death necessitate vigilant monitoring and timely electrophysiological intervention.

Research into the genetic and molecular basis of Ebstein's anomaly may provide insights into disease pathogenesis, potentially paving the way for targeted therapies. Advances in regenerative medicine and stem cell therapy offer hope for enhancing myocardial function and promoting recovery in cases with significant ventricular impairment.

In summary, Ebstein's anomaly exemplifies the complexities of congenital heart disease, requiring an individualized and dynamic approach to care. The integration of innovative diagnostic and therapeutic techniques has markedly improved the prognosis for many patients, transforming what was once a uniformly fatal condition into one with diverse and hopeful outcomes. However, the lifelong nature of the disease necessitates continuous surveillance and multidisciplinary care to optimize quality of life and long-term survival. Future research and technological advancements will undoubtedly further refine the management of this challenging condition, offering new avenues for treatment and improved outcomes for patients with Ebstein's anomaly.

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